

The Effects of pyrolysis scrubber liquids on anaerobic digestion of cow manure

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Abstract

The study evaluated the potential of anaerobic digestion (AD) as a waste management solution for scrubber liquids generated by the gas cleaning systems of a pyrolysis plant. Two distinct waste streams were analyzed using lab-scale batch tests. cow manure was used as a substrate while oil-based scrubber liquid and a water-based scrubber liquid were used as additives in different concentrations to tests their potential in AD process. The results showed that both scrubber liquids exhibited significant initial inhibitory effects on the AD process, characterized by prolonged lag phases. However, most tests demonstrated recovery over time, indicating microbial adaptation. This recovery suggests that, with appropriate acclimatization strategies, AD could represent a viable pathway for the sustainable management of pyrolysis scrubber liquids.

Keywords

Anaerobic digestion, Pyrolysis, Scrubber liquid

INTRODUCTION

Anaerobic digestion (AD) plays a pivotal role in the global transition toward sustainable energy systems. By converting organic waste into biogas and nutrient-rich digestate, AD provides a renewable alternative to fossil fuels while addressing waste management challenges. Recent research has focused on integrating AD with complementary technologies, such as pyrolysis, to enhance the overall sustainability and efficiency of waste valorization systems. Pyrolysis, a thermochemical process, transforms the solid fraction of digestate into valuable products including biochar, bio-oil, and syngas, which are aligned with the principles of the circular economy.

Despite these advantages, the pyrolysis process also generates secondary waste streams, particularly scrubber liquids produced during the cleaning of syngas. These liquids, derived from water or vegetable oil-based scrubbers, are critical for achieving high-efficiency tar removal up to 97.6%, when paired with char adsorption. However, their composition presents a new waste management challenge. Scrubber liquids are rich in tars, phenolics, aldehydes, and other complex organic compounds, many of which are classified as inhibitory or emerging contaminants. These compounds can significantly disrupt biological processes, including those central to AD, by impairing microbial activity and reducing biogas yields. For instance, phenolics at concentrations exceeding 1 g/L have been shown to severely inhibit methanogenesis, the critical final stage of biogas production [2].

These challenges complicate the direct integration of pyrolysis scrubber liquids into AD processes. However, previous studies have shown that microbial communities in AD systems can adapt over time to inhibitory substances particularly with strategies such as substrate dilution, acclimatization, and nutrient supplementation in order to improve biogas yields and stabilize microbial activity [2], suggesting that AD could offer a viable treatment pathway for pyrolysis-derived waste streams.

In this study, we evaluate the feasibility of using AD to treat pyrolysis scrubber liquids, including both water- and vegetable oil-based streams. Using a lab-scale batch custom-made AMPTs test. The research aims to assess biogas production potential and inhibitory effects during the treatment process. By investigating these aspects, this work seeks to provide critical insights into the integration of pyrolysis scrubber liquids into AD systems and their role in advancing sustainable waste management practices and renewable energy production.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Inoculum, Substrate, and scrubber liquids source and preparation

Anaerobic digestate from Nature Energy's Midtfyn a thermophilic biogas plant in Funen, Denmark, was used as an inoculum. Cow manure was also gathered from the Midtfyn biogas plant. The scrubber liquids both water- and oil-based were obtained from Frichs pyrolysis in Horsens, Denmark which is operating with digestate fibres. Before use the cow manure substrate was ground for 5 min to homogenise them and for ease operation. The total solids (TS) and volatile solids (VS) content of the inoculum, substrate, and scrubber liquid are given in Table 1. The two experiments were conducted using the same batch of inoculum and cow manure.

Table 1. Total Solids (TS) and Volatile Solids (VS) content of inoculum and substrates. Data are presented as averages from triplicates and standard deviations (SD)

	pH	TS%		VS%	
		(%)	(SD)	(%)	(SD)
Inoculum	8,06	6.2	0.03	6.62	0.1
Cow manure	7.38	8.0	0.17	4.25	0.12
Scrubber oil	7.91	93.6	0.43	93.51	0.06
Scrubber water	9.25	0.3	0.007	0.27	0.003

Analytical methods

The TS & VS were determined following the German standard VDI 4630 [4]. pH of inoculum, substrate, and scrubber liquids were measured using HQ440d multi pH meter by Hach. The methane yield was calculated based on the consensus methodology outlined by Holliger C. et.al.[3]. Volatile Fatty Acid (VFA) concentrations were analyzed according to the protocol in Ali, R et.al. [6].

Design and operation of batch fermentation experiments

The batch experiments used a 1L AMPTs-inspired system with 12 duplicate glass flasks incubated in a Memmert WNE 29 water bath at 52°C ($\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) for 35 days. Each flask had a mechanical stirrer operating at 60 rpm (1-minute mixing, 1-minute rest). Gas from each flask passed through 3 M NaOH to absorb CO₂, with CH₄ measured continuously using a Ritter MilliGascounter and Rigamo data logging software. Equivalent amounts of inoculum and cow manure were added for both experiments, with variations in scrubber liquid concentrations.

For the first experiment, scrubber water was added at volume concentrations ranging from 20% to 2%, with tap water making up the balance to a total working volume of 900 mL. For the second experiment, scrubber oil was tested at inoculum-to-substrate (IS) ratios ranging from 8:1 to 14:1, with a total working volume of 800 mL. Table 2 illustrate the experimental design for both experiments.

Table 2 Experimental design for batch test for the two separate experiments testing scrubber water and scrubber oil respectively.

Bottle	Exp. 1 setup	Added scrubber water [g]	Exp. 2 setup	Added scrubber Oil [g]
1 & 2	Blank	0	Blank	0
3 & 4	20%(v/v)	180	P*	16*
5 & 6	16%(v/v)	144	[8:1]	5.4
7 & 8	11%(v/v)	100	[10:1]	4.3
9 & 10	6%(v/v)	54	[12:1]	3.6
11 & 12	2.2%(v/v)	20	[14:1]	3.1

*Positive (P) control used was glucose

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Experiment 1: Impact of scrubber water on AD

The impact of scrubber water on anaerobic digestion (AD) performance was investigated by measuring cumulative biomethane production and relative percentage decreases in methane yield compared to the control (blank). The results, summarized in Table 3, reveal a clear trend of increasing inhibition with higher concentrations of scrubber water. Reactors with the highest concentrations (20% and 16% v/v) experienced complete process failure, producing negligible methane. At 11% v/v, a significant lag phase of approximately seven days was observed before methane production resumed, whereas reactors with 6% and 2.2% v/v exhibited more stable performance with progressively shorter lag phases and higher methane yields.

Table 3 Results of AMPT test showing effect of scrubber water on methane production

Bottle	Exp. 1 setup	Added scrubber water [g]	Start pH	Cumulative CH ₄ [L]	Relative decrease
1 & 2	Blank	0	7.9	5.3	-
3 & 4	20%(v/v)	180	9.12	0.1	-98.5%
5 & 6	16%(v/v)	144	9.1	0.1	-98.7%
7 & 8	11%(v/v)	100	8.9	1.4	-73,6%
9 & 10	6%(v/v)	54	8.8	2.4	-54.7%
11 & 12	2.2%(v/v)	20	8.4	4.3	-18.9%

The observed inhibition is attributed to two primary factors: hydrocarbons and elevated alkalinity. Scrubber water is rich in phenolics and other inhibitory compounds, which are known to impair microbial membrane integrity and enzymatic functions, especially for methanogens. The elevated alkalinity of the reactors with scrubber water had a high initial pH (8.4–9.12), which exceeds the optimal range for AD (6.8–7.4). This likely inhibited acidogenesis and methanogenesis, as supported by literature [5].

Volatile fatty acid (VFA) analysis (Figure 1) supports these findings, showing minimal consumption of butyric and propionic acids at higher scrubber water concentrations. The inhibition of acidogenesis is particularly evident at pH > 8.3, as acidogenic bacteria are sensitive to such conditions [5]. In reactors with lower concentrations of scrubber water (6% and 2.2%), most VFAs were consumed within 10–15 days, indicating partial recovery of microbial activity [5]. The experiment showed that scrubber water inhibits AD, with complete failure observed in flasks containing 20%(v/v) and 16%(v/v). Even at 11%(v/v), inhibition occurred initially, but methane production resumed after a prolonged lag phase of around 7 days.

Figure 1. VFA concentrations results of butyric, propionic and acetic acid as a function of days

Experiment 2: effect of scrubber oil effect on AD

The second experiment assessed the effects of scrubber oil on anaerobic digestion (AD), with cumulative biomethane production normalized to volatile solids (VS). As shown in Figure 2, all

reactors exhibited prolonged lag phases compared to the blank, indicating an initial inhibitory effect. Lower inoculum-to-substrate (IS) ratios (8:1 and 10:1) showed significant inhibition, likely caused by toxic compounds such as phenolics, which disrupt microbial activity. At higher IS ratios (12:1 and 14:1), positive Biochemical Methane Potential (BMP) values were observed, suggesting that increased inoculum levels diluted inhibitors and supported microbial adaptation.

Figure 2. Net BMP of scrubber oil with varying IS ratios

The prolonged lag phases at lower IS ratios emphasize the need for process optimization, such as inoculum acclimatization or substrate ratio adjustments, to mitigate the inhibitory effects of scrubber oil and improve AD performance. Methane accumulation from the blanks was subtracted from test flasks and normalized to VS to calculate the BMP.

CONCLUSION

Both pyrolysis scrubber oil and water scrubber liquids inhibited the AD process, with phenolics and high pH affecting the water scrubber and toxic organics impacting the oil scrubber. Methane production recovered over time under optimized conditions. Higher IS ratios reduced inhibition from oil scrubber liquids, while lower concentrations of water scrubber liquids allowed partial VFA consumption and methane production. These results suggest that with proper optimization, AD can effectively manage pyrolysis scrubber liquids while supporting renewable energy and waste valorisation.

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